

PECULIARITIES OF ORGANIZATIONAL STRATEGY FORMATION

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the results of a critical analysis of methodological approaches to the formation of organizational development strategies.

Key words: strategy, strategic management, strategic thinking, strategy formulation, strategic plan.

INTRODUCTION

The essence of all approaches to the formation of the organization's strategy is manifested in the unity of theoretical analysis and intuition of strategy developers (they are primarily the subjects who develop, detail and implement the strategy).

Also, a very important aspect to consider is that the strategy can never be completely calculated and thought out, its correction in accordance with the changes in the internal and external environment is a necessary procedure.

Based on this, it can be concluded that there is no one-size-fits-all method of strategy formation, but nevertheless, experience shows the possibility of using several possible directions in strategy formation.

METHODOLOGY

Harvard Business School is the leader in the formulation of strategy formulation procedures. K. Andrews, M. Porter, G. Hemel and K. Prahalad developed the main approaches to strategy formulation, the characteristics of which are presented in the table below:

1 – table. Approaches to strategy development.

Creators	The main essence of the study	Strategy	Period
K. Andrews	SWOT analysis	Economical	1970 s
M. Porter	The five forces of competition,exemplary strategies	Business strategy	1980s
G. Hemel and K. Prahalad	Basic powers	Leadership strategy	1990s

K. Andrews proposed a strategy based on the compatibility between the existing market opportunities and the organization’s opportunities at the defined risk level. The competitive position of the organization, as well as the approaches to formulating a business strategy based on competitive strategies were developed by M. Porter, and the concept of core competencies by K. Prahalad and G. Designed by Hemellar.

Traditional methods of strategy formulation. A SWOT analysis of the organization’s external and internal parameters, which is familiar to every manager today, makes it possible to determine the following:

- identification of opportunities and risks;
- Creating a SWOT analysis matrix;
- determining the markets where goods and goods are intended to be sold;
- formation of an economic strategy (with determination of the necessary and obtainable resources for the implementation of the strategy).

The analysis of the five forces model of competition allows to determine the strong and weak positions of the organization in the market and the areas where strategic changes can give the maximum result for the development of the business.

According to M. Porter, the following is necessary:

- determination of an advantageous (priority) position in the market that provides the best protection from the five forces of competition;
- making a forecast of the possible level of profitability of the network;
- development of activities aimed at taking the most advantageous (priority) position in the market.

Core competencies, as a unique feature that provides leadership positions among competitors, form the basis of strategy formulation within the following procedures:

- to determine the unique features of the organization and its product;
- assessment of collective skills (systematic competence set) of the organization’s employees;
- focusing the organization’s attention on the main competencies that form the basis of the strategy;

- ensuring non-return of the main powers of the organization;
- forming a leadership strategy.

Matrix method of strategy formulation

DEVELOPMENT OF THE ORGANIZATION'S GOAL

The difference in the internal and external environment of the organization explains the diversity of the organizations and their actual situation. The large number of parameters that determine the state of the organization, taken separately, does not give the opportunity to systematize them and the process of developing the existing and expected image of the organization.

The different life experience of the employees of the organization leads to different interpretations of the same event, losses, errors, etc. in the verbal classification of organizations. requires a long and arduous way of adapting ideas from a social point of view. Therefore, it is effective to "paint pictures" (today and expected state of the organization) and to identify the "discontinuity" between the dreams and the actual situation.

Outside observation is directed to assess opportunities and risks, to determine the competitive situation of the organization and its compliance with one of the model strategies, in addition to determining which of the resources is coming to organizations and what products are supplied to the external environment as a result of processing these resources. Monitoring from within the organization will focus on classifying the capabilities (strengths) of the organization and existing problems, determining the main competencies of the organization, as well as the characteristics of Personnel Management and the direction of the organization. At this stage, the transformation of many autumn calls into a system with the present and future of the organization requires special skills. The table below presents examples of the classification of the target.

Table 2. Examples of target classification.

Organization	The essence of the goal
General Electric	Being the most competitive firm in the world, reaching the first or second place in every area of our activity.
Дисней компанияси	Making people happy
Compag Computer	Leading in the supply of personal computers and servers to them in all segments of the market

Organization mission. Since the organization is a platform for development motivation, the mission reflects the wishes of the leader and his team. Therefore, when developing a mission, not only the relationship of the organization with the potential iva external environment is taken into account, but also the compatibility of the goals

of the subjects, the image of the organization, the state of the manufactured product and many other factors. Consulting industry experts suggest using templates that reflect customer satisfaction when working out a mission. This method is essentially the identification of the main customers and their requirements, and then the selection of methods for satisfying these requirements by the organization.

The “outbound” mission, which is reflected in the Matrix as five directions, is rashedifrocated to the meaning of the parameters corresponding to the specific description of the organization in question. The specified descriptions are drawn up and entered into a table and grouped (for example, depending on the degree of importance for the organization). In a similar way, the parameters of the internal environment of the organization are assessed: the characteristic of the organization corresponding to them is determined and grouped. The mission, drawn up in a final way, must take into its composition the most important characteristics of the organization. Examples of the formation of the mission of various organizations are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Mission formation.

Organization	The essence of the mission
Microsoft	Computer to every household
Pepsi-Cola	Go ahead of Coca!
Lukoil	Being the only company in the world
Chevron	Formation of higher values for shareholders, consumers and employees

Organization purpose

After the formalization of the mission, one proceeds to develop (clarify) the strategic goals of the organization. Well-known Dutch consultant X.Wessema has identified three types of strategic goals:

- corporate (organization goals in general);
- business goals (goals of a group of activities of one type);
- functional (functional activity goals). Such an approach does not take into

account the influence of the external environment and the goals of the organization as a system.

Formalization of the organization’s goals in the final form is accepted at the level of intuition at the expense of its multi-factor nature, but all formalized goals are used in one way or another when detailing the organization’s strategy. Examples of the strategic goals of the organization are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Examples of the purpose of the organization

Organization	Content of goals
McDonalds	Achieve 100% satisfaction of customer requirements every day in every restaurant
McCormick & Company	Achieve a 20% income level on shares. Annual increase in the volume of net sales to 10%. Ensuring that the average annual growth rate of earnings on shares is 15%. Direct 25-30% of net profit to the payment of dividends

In conclusion, the strategy, on the one hand, is aimed at eliminating the interruption between the current state and the expected prospect, and on the other – concentrates on the main content of strategic goals, expressed in the previous step.

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